

Notes

Intake of Calcium and Magnesium by Indian Clay Minerals

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CALCIUM and magnesium are well known essential secondary elements that are required by plants for their good growth and development. Since clays and clay minerals are important factors in soils that direct their availability and retention, an attempt has been made in this paper to study the extent of intake of calcium and magnesium from solutions of calcium and magnesium chloride by three important clay minerals viz., kaolinite, illite and bentonite at 20°, 30° and 40°. A search of the literature will show that this aspect of

and the volume was made up by adding the requisite quantity of water. The flasks were kept in a thermostat maintained at a particular temperature (20°, 30° or 40°) and the adsorption experiments were carried out at the required temperatures both for the single and combined ions of calcium and magnesium. The terms "intake" and "adsorption" are used here synonymously.

Results and Discussion

A perusal of table 1 will show that at all the three temperatures, calcium and magnesium intake by bentonite is maximum and there is almost no difference in the values obtained for illite and kaolinite. It is known¹ that of the three clay minerals, montmorillonite is formed naturally more under conditions where there is good base supply and this condition is not as much required by illite and kaolinite although illite formation does not take place in acidic condition as is required for kaolinite¹. The structure of montmorillonite

TABLE-1. INTAKE OF CALCIUM AND MAGNESIUM FROM THEIR CHLORIDES IN AQUEOUS MEDIA AT 20°, 30° AND 40°

Clay Minerals	Initial Conc. mg/25 ml		Adsorption (x/m)					
			20°		30°		40°	
			Ca	Mg	Ca	Mg	Ca	Mg
Kaolinite	40.08	24.32	37.07	22.61	37.02	22.62	36.96	22.62
	20.04	12.16	18.76	11.36	18.50	11.33	18.50	11.30
	10.02	6.08	9.24	5.64	9.27	5.61	9.24	5.64
	5.01	3.04	4.67	2.84	4.64	2.83	4.64	2.77
	2.50	1.52	2.32	1.41	2.29	1.40	2.32	1.40
Illite	40.08	24.32	37.00	22.62	37.03	22.61	36.98	22.58
	20.04	12.16	18.51	11.30	18.51	11.35	18.51	11.31
	10.02	6.08	9.29	5.66	9.31	5.67	9.28	5.61
	5.01	3.04	4.64	2.83	4.65	2.82	4.63	2.83
	2.50	1.52	2.32	1.42	2.32	1.40	2.32	1.41
Bentonite	40.08	24.32	37.13	22.69	37.17	22.70	37.17	22.69
	20.04	12.16	18.66	11.43	18.65	11.35	18.63	11.38
	10.02	6.08	9.42	5.74	9.39	5.75	9.40	5.71
	5.10	3.04	4.78	2.90	4.75	2.91	4.77	2.90
	2.50	1.52	2.39	1.48	2.38	1.46	2.39	1.47

study is yet to be taken up especially with the Indian clay minerals at the three temperatures mentioned earlier.

Experimental

The study of intake of calcium and magnesium was done from their chloride solutions by three pure clay minerals viz., montmorillonite, illite and kaolinite. These clay minerals were identified earlier by X-ray analysis.

For the intake (adsorption) study, 0.25g of the clay minerals taken in 100 ml. volumetric flasks, was treated with the respective solutions (M/25, M/50, M/100, M/200 and M/400) of calcium and magnesium chlorides

therefore develops in a fashion that will have naturally greater capacity for the intake of these two basic ions.

In presence of each other (table 2), the total intake of calcium and magnesium remains the same when compared with the intake values of calcium and magnesium singly. Under this condition, their combined intake is maximum with bentonite at 20° and at 40° this was maximum with kaolinite.

In general, at all the three temperatures, intake of calcium by the three clay minerals is maximum in comparison to magnesium.

TABLE—2. INTAKE OF CA+MG FROM THEIR MIXED CHLORIDE SOLUTIONS AT 20°, 30° AND 40°.

Clay Minerals	Initial Conc. mg./25 ml	Adsorption (x/m)		
		20°	30°	40°
Kaolinite	24.32	22.59	22.62	22.60
	22.16	11.26	11.23	11.33
	6.08	5.61	5.59	5.60
	3.04	2.82	2.80	3.04
	1.52	1.41	1.42	1.50
Illite	24.22	22.63	22.61	22.59
	12.16	11.28	12.09	11.22
	6.08	5.63	5.59	5.57
	3.04	2.81	2.82	2.81
	1.52	1.30	1.40	1.40
Bentonite	24.32	27.77	22.81	23.69
	12.16	11.34	11.31	11.28
	6.08	5.66	5.66	5.63
	3.04	2.87	2.87	2.83
	1.52	1.45	1.46	1.41

The adsorption of calcium and magnesium by the three clay minerals under all conditions appears to be exothermic or their maximum intake is observed to be at 20°. This intake appears to occur in multimolecular layers as their adsorption values do not obey Langmuir's equation of adsorption.

References

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214°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = 47^\circ$ (in CHCl_3), m.p. of benzoate derivative = 264°. The compound gave positive Salkowsky reaction², Libermann—Burchard reaction³, red colour with Noller's reagent⁴, reddish violet colour in Brieskorn test⁵, Tischugajen reaction⁶ and yellow colour with tetra nitromethane⁷ Ruzicka. Thus it is identified as Lupeol. Mixed melting point determination with an authentic sample of lupeol also confirmed its identity as lupeol.

The identification of this compound is further supported by spectral data, U. V. (Methanol) $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 200 \text{ m}\mu$ I. R. (KBr) = 3235 (M), 1640 (W), 1490 (W), 1382 (M), 1185 (W), 1105 (W), 1040 (W), 114 (W), 985 (W), 945 (W) cm^{-1} , N.M.R. in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal standard, showed signals at 4.64 and 3.18 τ .

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Lupeol from the seed of *Lycopersicon esculentum*

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Chemical Examination of Stem Cuttings of *Pterospermum heyneanum* Wall

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*LYCOSPERSICON esculentum*¹ belongs to the family Solanaceae and is rich in Vitamins A and C.

Experimental

Dried and finely powdered seed of *L. esculentum* on extraction with petroleum ether (40–60°) in a soxhlet extractor and the extract on concentration (150 ml) yielded a greenish white deposit (0.9 gm). The deposit was dissolved in hot methanol and when cooled, a white mass (0.7 gm) was separated, which on crystallisation yielded a white crystalline compound m. p. 213.5°, C = 84.43%, H = 11.62%, molecular weight by semi-micro rast = 399, molecular formula $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = 27^\circ$ (in CHCl_3), m. p. of acetylated derivative

PLANT. *Pterospermum heyneanum* (N. O. Leguminosae). Uses. medicinal.¹ Previous work. Nil. Present work. Powdered, air dried stem cuttings were extracted with hot ethanol. The viscous mass obtained on concentration under reduced pressure was then extracted successively with petroleum ether, benzene, ether, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol. The petroleum ether extract, on concentration, deposited a yellow solid which on chromatography over neutral alumina, followed by preparative T.L.C. yielded a compound, m.p. 13'–7°, which was identified as β -sitosterol² (m.p. m.m.p. superimposable IR).

The ether extract obtained was concentrated, dried, chromatographed over a column of silica gel. Elution with ethyl acetate, yielded another compound, molecular formula, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6$, m.p. 276–8°. It was